

Synthesis and properties of BD-HMHEC and its applications in oilfields

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Abstract : Dodecyl carbon chains of bromodecane (BD) were applied to the hydrophilic molecular chains of hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC) by the macromolecule reaction method to prepare hydrophobically associating hydroxyethyl cellulose (BD-HMHEC). The structures and properties of the BD-HMHEC were characterized by infrared spectrometer and viscosimeter. Optimum conditions of synthesis were gained through single factor experiments : reaction temperature was 80 °C, active agent's concentration was 3.0%, HEC's concentration was 9.0%, hydrophobic monomer's concentration was 3.3% and reaction time was 5 h. BD-HMHEC has been firstly successfully utilized to the oilfield pilot development for profile controlling of Block LP in Zhongyuan Oilfield and enhancing oil recovery of Block A-3 in Daqing Oilfield, China.

Keywords : Hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC), bromodecane (BD), hydrophobic modification, thickening viscosity, oilfields.

Introduction

Water-soluble polymer flooding has been verified as a mature technique used for many years in reservoirs. Commercially, available traditional polymers employed such as partially hydrolyzed polyacrylamide (HPAM) and biopolymers (e.g. xanthan gum) which results in increased solution viscosity, have been the objective of recent developments in enhanced oil recovery (EOR)^{1,2}. Certainly, there are some limitations and drawbacks of the traditional polymers at harsh reservoir conditions. Hydrophobically modified (or associated) water-soluble polymer (HM-polymer), as a novel polymer fluid, has a small number of hydrophobic groups attached directly to the macromolecular chain of traditional water-soluble polymers³.

Unlike the conventional water-soluble polymers in oilfields, HM-polymers usually have special rheological properties such as better thickening, thermal resistance, salt tolerance, shear resistance and acid/alkali-resistance. It is relevant also for the current demand with relatively low-price and environmental-friendly materials in various applications in EOR. A variety of HM-polymers have been studied in many oilfield operations^{2,4-7}.

The synthesis, rheology and oil displacement perfor-

mance of hydrophobically modified polyacrylamide (HM-PAM) have been extensively studied^{1,2}, which could enhance oil recovery and production after water flooding. Compared to HAPM⁹, the interest in hydrophobically modified ethoxylated urethane (HM-EUR) polymers focused on basic research and applications which can deeply understand associated polymers^{2,11}. Hydrophobically modified alkali-swelling emulsion (HM-ASE) are terpolymers, which have not been investigated as deeply and extensively as the HM-PAM or HM-EUR^{2,12}. NVP-HRAM were synthesized and evaluated by comparison with HPAM by sand-pack flood experiments, which can enhance uniform sweep efficiency, hence improving oil recovery^{13,14}. A series of hydrophobically modified amphoteric polymers (HM-AP) were evaluated by sand-pack flood experiments, which indicated HM-AP was suitable for use under hostile reservoir conditions¹⁵. Hydrophobically modified hydroxyethyl cellulose (HM-HEC) polymers are the most significant types, that are prepared by hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC) reaction with alkyl halides, acid anhydrides, acid halides, epoxides or isocyanates^{1,2,16}. HM-HEC polymers have much better thickening ability and stronger strain hardening behavior than their parent (HEC)^{6,17}. It has a prospective and of prac-

tical significance to use HEC to replace toxic and non-degradable synthetic polymers in EOR^{18,19}.

For HM-HEC, previous research mainly focused on the evaluation of the associated mechanism, rheological performance and special properties of HM-HEC solution, while failing to consider it as a good oil displacement system or a profile controlling agent^{20,21}. For its utilization in EOR fields, there are two innovations of this paper. On the one hand, a new kind of HM-polymers named hydrophobically associated hydroxyethyl cellulose (BD-HMHEC) was synthesized using dodecyl carbon chains of bromodecane (BD) and hydrophilic molecular chains of hydroxyethyl cellulose (HEC) through the macromolecule reaction method. Optimum conditions of synthesis including reaction temperature, active agent's concentration, HEC's concentration, hydrophobic monomer's concentration and reaction time were achieved through single factor experiments. On the other hand, BD-HMHEC has been firstly successfully utilized to the field pilot development for profile controlling of Block LP in Zhongyuan Oilfield and enhancing oil recovery of Block A-3 in Daqing Oilfield, China.

Experimental

Materials :

Formation sand, crude oil, and formation water were from Block LP in Zhongyuan Oilfield and Block A-3 in Daqing Oilfield, China. The materials used were acetic acid, aqueous acetone, NaCl, NaOH and hydrochloride solution (37%), solvents, HPAM (molecular weight : ~ 14 million), HEC (molecular weight : ~ 1.3 million), which were all supplied by MERCK-Schuchardt Ltd. (Germany). 1-Bromodecane (BD, C₁₂H₂₅Br) and IPA were supplied by Tianshi Chemical Reagent Co. Ltd. (China). The experimental gas was high-pressure nitrogen (N₂).

Synthesis method and procedure :

BD-HMHEC was synthesized using dodecyl carbon chains of BD (C₁₂H₂₅Br) and the hydrophilic molecular chains of HEC through Williamson etherification reaction in the laboratory^{22,23}. The synthesis procedures of BD-HMHEC were as follows : An amount of HEC mixed with an appropriate amount of IPA was put in a three-neck flask (250 mL) and stirred for 20 min. A certain concentration of NaOH solution was slowly added into the mixture, then, the solution was simultaneously purged

with N₂ for 20 min. The mixture was swelled and activated for 24 h at room temperature. The BD dissolved in IPA was put into the mixture after the flask had been heated to 55 °C. After the reaction, the mixtures above were rapidly cooled with cold water. The residue was washed and filtrated with hexane and acetone solution and then adjusted to a certain pH value (7~8) with glacial acetic acid. The product was dried for 5 h in a vacuum condition, and then the solid product was named "BD-HMHEC", whose molecular structure is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of BD-HMHEC molecular structure.

Characterizations :

Composition and structure of the polymer molecule were qualitatively analyzed using VERTEX-70 type infrared spectrometer, the infrared spectrogram of HEC and BD-HMHEC were obtained in Fig. 2(a) and 2(b).

From Fig. 2(a) and 2(b), absorption peaks near 1375 cm⁻¹ and 1450 cm⁻¹ of hydrophobic modified HEC changed to varying degrees, the point of which were respectively the symmetric bending vibration peak of methyl and the asymmetric one of methylene, whereas, increase of peak reflected increase in the molecular structure of alkanes. It was confirmed that the long chain alkane group -C₁₂H₂₅ has been introduced into the macromolecular chain of hydrophobic modified HEC and BD-HMHEC was created.

Results and discussion

The optimum synthesis conditions and results of BD-HMHEC were discussed and gained through single factor experiments. The synthesis conditions were initially designed as follows : The concentrations of HEC and active agent (NaOH) were respectively 8.0% and 3.0%, the amount of BD was 2.7% and reaction time was 4 h.

Fig. 3 shows the effects of the synthetic parameters (such as reaction temperature, activator's concentration,

Fig. 2. Fourier transform infrared-red (FT-IR) spectra of HEC and BD-HMHEC.

HEC's concentration, hydrophobic monomer dosage and reaction time, etc.) on the apparent viscosity (μ_a) of BD-HMHEC.

Effect of the reaction temperature on μ_a :

Fig. 3(a) shows the effect of reaction temperature on μ_a of BD-HMHEC. From Fig. 3(a), μ_a increased gradually with the increase in reaction temperature. When the reaction temperature was low (e.g. 40~60 °C), μ_a was low, and the thickening property was poor as a result of BD not being introduced into HEC's molecular chains. When the reaction temperature reached 60 °C, μ_a increased significantly, this resulted from BD being effectively introduced into HEC's molecular chain. When the reaction temperature reached 80 °C, the maximum μ_a was obtained, which indicated that the optimal thickening effect and the higher hydrophobic modification were achieved. Moreover, the reaction did not choose a higher temperature path, because the boiling point of organic solvent (isopropanol) is 82 °C. If the reaction temperature rises continually, a large number of isopropanol will volatile, resulting in HEC not uniformly dispersing in the organic phase, hence greatly reducing the degree of hydrophobic modification. To sum up, the optimum reaction temperature to synthesize BD-HMHEC was 80 °C.

Effect of the activator concentration on μ_a :

After the optimum reaction temperature has been determined as 80 °C, HEC was pretreated by NaOH solution (other parameters were the same as above). Fig. 3(b)

shows the effect of the activator concentration on μ_a of BD-HMHEC.

From Fig. 3(b), when the activator's concentration was less than 3.0%, μ_a rose rapidly with the increase in the activator concentration, then it reached the maximum value when the concentration was 3.0%. At a low concentration (e.g. 1.5% and 2.0%), BD-HMHEC swelled and became mushy and viscous, which resulted in the Weissenberg effect (Fig. 4). It was difficult to disperse in HEC because the hydrophobic monomer of BD dissolved in isopropanol, which made the reaction degree low and the thickening effect not ideal. When the concentration was greater than 3.0%, μ_a dropped rapidly and then kept steady at 4.0%. At high concentration (e.g. 6.0% and 8.0%), HEC was precipitated at the bottom of the reactor, while hydrophobic monomers dissolved in isopropanol were at the top, the reaction only occurred at interface between the two phases. The reaction and the hydrophobically modified degree were low, and the thickening property was poor. Therefore, the optimum reaction concentration of the activator was 3.0%.

Effect of HEC's concentration on μ_a :

HEC's concentration directly affects its swelling process and accessibility. Only under the condition of fully swelling or dissolving are all hydroxyls of HEC reachable and available for the reaction molecules. After the optimum reaction temperature (80 °C) and reaction concentration of the activator (3.0%) had been determined,

(a) Reaction Temperature

(b) Activator concentration

(c) HEC concentration

(d) Bromododecane dosage

(e) Reaction Time

Fig. 3. Effects of synthetic parameters on apparent viscosity of BD-HMHEC.

concentration of BD and reaction time were set at 2.7% and 4 h respectively. Fig. 3(c) shows the effect of HEC's concentration on μ_a of BD-HMHEC.

From Fig. 3(c), μ_a firstly increased and then decreased with the increase in HEC's concentration. At higher concentrations (e.g. 11.0%), μ_a was low, which showed it was less for the hydrophobic groups $-C_{12}H_{25}$ to be introduced to HEC's molecular chain when the reaction system was divided into two phases. It was difficult for BD in the oil phase to disperse into HEC at the bottom, and the reaction degree was low. With the decrease in HEC's concentration until it reached 9.0%, μ_a obviously increased, and the reaction system turned into uniform slurry, which was beneficial to the dispersion of hydrophobic monomer resulting in a higher thickening property. However, decreasing HEC's concentration also had a certain limit only because, at low concentrations, the contact probability between the reactants would reduce which results in a poor thickening property. So the optimum HEC's concentration was 9.0%.

Effect of the hydrophobic monomer dosage on μ_a :

The amount of the hydrophobic monomer dosage directly affects the contact probability between the hydrophobic monomer with the hydroxyl on the molecular chain of HEC and their hydrophobically modified degree of reaction. After the optimum reaction temperature (80 °C), activator's concentration (3.0%) and HEC's concentration of (9.0%) had been determined, respectively, reaction time was set to 4 h. Fig. 3(d) shows the effect of hydrophobic monomer dosage on μ_a of BD-HMHEC.

From Fig. 3(d), μ_a firstly increased and then decreased with the increase of BD dosage. When the dosage was little (e.g. 1.6%), it was low for the contact probability between BD with HEC, resulting in a low μ_a . With the increase of BD dosage (e.g. 2.2%, 2.7% and 3.3%), contact probability between them and the aggregation degree of BD were increased, leading to improvement of the thickening property. When the BD dosage was continuously increased (e.g. 3.8%), due to its high molecular aggregation degree, it was then difficult for the BD molecules entering into interior HEC's molecule, which caused the reaction to become nonuniform and μ_a was then decreased. If its dosage continuously increased (e.g. 4.4%), the intermolecular hydrophobic association is then

too strong to separate for the associated phase, which causes μ_a to drop rapidly. So the optimum BD dosage was 3.3%.

Effect of the reaction time on μ_a :

After the optimum reaction temperature (80 °C), reaction concentrations of the activator (3.0%), HEC's concentration (9.0%) and the reaction time (4.0 h) had been determined, respectively, Fig. 3(e) shows the effect of the reaction time on μ_a in BD-HMHEC.

From Fig. 3(e), μ_a firstly increased and then decreased with the increase of the reaction time. When reaction time was short (e.g. 3.0 h and 4.0 h), reaction degree was not enough, resulting in poor thickening property; when reaction time was increased to 5.0 h, μ_a reached maximal value, which meant that HEC's molecular chains effectively linked the hydrophobic groups and BD-HMHEC solution began to form supramolecular aggregates of space network structure. If the reaction time were further extended, the quantity of BD linked on HEC's molecule would be too large, and the hydrophobic association would be too strong which reduced the water solubility and thickening property. Thus, the optimum reaction time was 5.0 h.

Fig. 4. Weissenberg effect.

Applications of BD-HMHEC in oilfield pilots :

Block LP of Zhongyuan Oilfield in China is a typical high-salinity, high-temperature reservoir; because of high-speed development of water injection, it was in an invalid water-injection-cycle stage at the end of 2012, resulting in a high water cut and low oil production. In January 2013, profile control and water shutoff were conducted using BD-HMHEC as the main profile-controlling sys-

tem. They were effective in 28 of the 35 oil wells with an effective rate of 80%; 22 injected wells were restored, average injection water for a single well was increased to 10 m³/d, injection pressure was increased to 3.0 MPa. The incremental oil production was 36 t per day at an early stage, 47 t per day at the peak period. By the end of December, the cumulative incremental oil was 5374 t; polymer-oil displacement rate reached 46 t/t, which obtained the good effect of the profile control and the water shutoff. Thus, BD-HMHEC has good properties of viscosifying, thermal resistance and salt tolerance under the high-salinity and high-temperature reservoir conditions.

Block A-3 of Daqing Oilfield in China is a high porosity and permeability reservoir that was developed by water flooding since 1973. At the end of 2011, the water cut reached 98% again, and the incremental oil recovery by HAPM flooding was only 15.5%. In order to maximize the oil recovery, the pilot test of BD-HMHEC flooding was carried out since January 1, 2012. By the end of 2013, BD-HMHEC flooding has increased by 8.7% incremental oil recovery after HAPM flooding.

From the results observed in pilot tests, BD-HMHEC exhibited good temperature and salinity tolerance and shear resistance performance as well as better oil displacement property whether employing it as profile modification system or as polymer displace agent. The good results obtained whether under high salinity and high-temperature reservoirs or high porosity and permeability reservoirs, thus widening BD-HMHEC application scope in EOR area.

Conclusions

The optimum conditions to synthesize BD-HMHEC were achieved : reaction temperature was 80 °C, active agent concentration was 3.0%, HEC concentration was 9.0%, hydrophobic monomer concentration was 3.3% and reaction time was 5.0 h. BD-HMHEC has been successfully utilized in the field pilot development for profile controlling of Block LP in Zhongyuan Oilfield and enhancing oil recovery of Block A-3 in Daqing Oilfield, China. Good results have been obtained whether under high-salinity and high-temperature reservoirs or high porosity and permeability reservoirs, thus widening BD-HMHEC application scope in EOR area.

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References

1. K. C. Taylor and H. A. Nasr-El-Din, *J. Pet. Sci. Eng.*, 1998, **19**, 265.
2. D. A. Z. Wever, F. Picchioni and A. A. Broekhuis, *Prog. Polym. Sci.*, 2011, **36**, 1558.
3. C. L. McCormick, P. A. Callais and B. H. Hutchinson (Jr.), *Macromol.*, 1985, **18**, 2394.
4. A. Hill, F. Candau and J. Selb, *Macromol.*, 1993, **26**, 4521.
5. T. Annable, R. Buscall, R. Ettelaie and D. Whittlestone, *J. Rheol.*, 1993, **37**, 695.
6. R. J. English, J. H. Laurer, R. J. Spontak and S. A. Khan, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, 2001, **41**, 6425.
7. X. Y. Zhao, Z. Y. Sun, J. Q. Ji, X. Cai, F. Yang and T. H. Wang, *Mater. Res. Innov.*, 2014, **18**, 451.
8. H. Chen, L. J. Han, P. Xu and P. Y. Luo, *Acta Phys-Chim. Sin.*, 2003, **19**, 1020.
9. K. C. Tam, R. D. Jenkins, M. A. Winnik and D. R. Bassett, *Macromol.*, 1998, **31**, 4149.
10. M. Huldén, *Colloids and Surf. (A)*, 1994, **82**, 263.
11. D. Liao, S. Dai and K. C. Tam, *Polym.*, 2004, **45**, 8339.
12. R. J. English, S. R. Raghavan, R. D. Jenkins and S. A. Khan, *J. Rheol.*, 1999, **43**, 1175.
13. J. Bock, S. J. Pace and D. N. Schulz, U.S. Patent No. 4709759, 1987.
14. S. Evani, U. S. Patent No. 4814096, 1989.
15. J. Wang, Y. Zheng, Y. J. Feng and P. Y. Luo, *Oilfield Chem.*, 1991, **16**, 1.
16. L. M. Landoll, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1982, **20**, 443.
17. E. Volpert, J. Selb and F. Candau, *Polym.*, 1998, **39**, 1025.
18. D. B. Braun, L. B. I. George, E. D. Goddard, R. L. Kreege and M. M. I. Frederick, U.S. Patent No. 4663159, 1987.
19. R. Donges, C. Meister, W. Schermann and W. Schratzenholz, U.S. Patent No. 5302196, 1994.
20. H. A. Nasr-El-Din, B. F. Hawkins and K. A. Green, SPE 21028-MS, 1991, 293-306.
21. M. Lin, Q. Zhao, S. Dang, Y. Wang, Y. Wang and X. Wang, *Mater. Res. Innov.*, 2015, **19**, 574.
22. Y. L. Wang, D. X. Qiu and G. C. Jiang, Pat. CN102, 140,337A, 2013.
23. L. Ye, Q. Li, Y. Cai, R. H. Huang and H. Dai, Pat. CN1, 560,083A, 2004.